

The material expression of new pulp-fibre reinforced composites in relation to other material categories

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Abstract To help bridge the gap between the science lab and commercial production there is a need for a better understanding of how new bio-based materials are perceived by users. The aim of the studies in this paper was to identify the material expression, sensorial properties and semantic dimensions of a group of pulp-fibre reinforced composites that are still in the research phase and how these relate to other, better-known materials already on the market. The studies involved 21 different materials, divided into different material groups such as metals, solid woods, wood fibre materials, plastic and fibre-reinforced composites in which the pulp-fibre reinforced composites were included. The materials were evaluated for meaning in a product semantic study and for sensory perception in a sensorial study. The results of the semantic study gave two underlining dimensions explaining most of the variations between the materials, Quality and Naturalness. These dimensions also had strong correlations to some of the sensorial properties. The results indicate that the pulp-fibre reinforced composites were not perceived as having high quality or expressing naturalness. They were hard to distinguish from the plastics in the study. The implications for further research and material development are discussed.

Keywords *Affective meaning, Sensorial properties, Pulp-fibre reinforced composites, New material, Material experience*

Introduction

When developing new materials, the material scientist's focus is on the material's technical properties and production aspects. But to be able to foresee for which applications a material is most suited, there is also a need for knowledge about the end user's (i.e., the consumer's) experience of the material. Without this knowledge there is a risk that the material will not succeed on today's competitive market. The material is the interface between the user and the product and a large part of the making of the product experience. The material not only provides the technical function of the product, it also plays a part in creating the product's expression and personality (Ashby & Johnson, 2010). Bio-based materials will play an important role in making our future more sustainable, and while these materials are indeed emerging on the market, most of them are still in the research phase of their development. Previous studies in the field of material experience have concluded that there is a big gap in the knowledge of how these new materials are appraised by users (Karana & Nijkamp, 2014).

Users experience a material through a sensory interaction with the material, which elicits aesthetic, cognitive and emotional responses (Hekkert & Karana, 2014). The way the user interacts with the material, what type of product the material is placed in, the combination of materials, the situation in which the

interaction take place, and the experience, cultural background, gender, age and concerns of the user, all affect the user's aesthetic, cognitive and emotional response to the material (Karana, 2009). This means that the material expression is not fixed but dynamic. However, according to Ashby and Johnson (2010), all material has a character that is hidden within the material, "a sort of embedded personality, a shy one, not always visible, easily concealed or disguised, but one that, when appropriately manipulated, can contribute to good design" (p. 82). Hekkert and Karana use the term universal meanings of materials to describe a similar quality, meanings not sensitive to individual or cultural differences or type of context. But they are more restrictive in using this term and suggest that meanings of newer materials, with a shorter history of use than wood or steel, have to be learned and therefore are more flexible and not universal (Hekkert & Karana, 2014).

New materials have no history when it comes to context of use and shaping. Users have no prior experience of the material and therefore no associations connected directly to it. This limits the way we can study these materials' expressive qualities and their meanings as the meanings will develop with use. We can try to find the "hidden personality" (Ashby & Johnson, 2010) of the material by studying it in different ways. The different meanings a material evokes are partly based on the sensorial and technical

properties of the material (Karana, 2009), and therefore it will be possible to study the meanings with strong connections to these properties even though the material is not yet placed in a product and a user context.

The importance of the different senses in product experience varies according to product type and type of usage situation (Schifferstein & Wastiels, 2014). When studying a new material there is no knowledge about the type of product and usage situation the material is going to be in. The visual and tactile senses are the two most dominant channels when it comes to product experience in general, according to previous studies (Schifferstein & Cleiren, 2005; Schifferstein & Desmet, 2007; Schifferstein & Wastiels, 2014). The senses of vision and touch complement each other in that they give rise to different types of associations when experiencing materials. A series of studies by Wastiels, Schifferstein, Wouters and Heylighen (2013) showed that when only touching a material, users describe the sensory properties of the material, but when using vision only they describe more meanings they associate to the material (Wastiels et al., 2013). In this study, the respondents use both vision and touch to evaluate the materials.

There have been some recent studies on new bio-based materials. The relation between perception and preferences, on different wood-based and pulp-based composites compared to solid wood and wood-based panels, was studied by Jonsson, Lindberg, Roos, Hugosson and Lindström (2008). In another study, wood and pulp-based composites were evaluated together with solid wood and wood fibre materials, in order to see how the tactile perception related to the experienced meaning of the materials (Lindberg, Roos, Kihlstedt, & Lindström, 2013). In yet another study, bio plastics were evaluated in two different products to determine how fibreness, reflectiveness and roughness affect the perception of naturalness and high quality (Karana & Nijkamp, 2014).

We have chosen to investigate pulp-fibre reinforced composites that are under development at the moment. The material scientists developing these materials know a lot about the technical and mechanical properties, but often less about the expression conveyed by these materials. In order to move these materials from the research lab to the market, there is a need to know more about how they are perceived by end users. By knowing more about the users' experience it will be easier to see which applications the materials are best suited for and also to estimate the market potential of the materials. We believe such knowledge will help bridge the gap between science lab and commercial production. In order to understand how these new materials are perceived, a first step would be to compare them against a wide range of other well-known materials such as different metals, solid woods, plastics, wood-fibre based materials and other fibre-reinforced composites. By comparing the perceived features of the different materials we aim to find the unique qualities of these new materials that set them apart from other materials.

Material and method

Two studies were performed in which injection-moulded pulp-fibre reinforced composites were evaluated together with other already known materials. The studies have focused on two different kinds of user evaluations: sensorial properties and affective meaning using a product semantic approach (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984).

Sensorial scale

The sensorial scales used for sensory evaluation were based on Elvin Karana's scales used in her 'meaning of materials' tool (Karana, 2009). The words describing the different sensorial properties were freely translated to Swedish. The order in which they appear were changed so that properties relating to tactile exploration were presented first and the visual properties after, in order to make it easier for the respondents to see what sensory domain to use when evaluating each property. Two tactile properties (friction and dryness) were added which were deemed important when comparing the specific materials in the study. Also added to the visual properties was the degree of visual pattern from low to high (Jonsson et al., 2008). The visual pattern was described as degree of visual variation on the surface. This property was added to be able to evaluate how the grain in the composites or the wood affected the perception of the material. The pictograms used in the scales were slightly modified by Edström and Borelius (Borelius & Edström, 2013).

Semantic scale

The descriptive words used for association to the samples were based on earlier elicitation studies on wood and wood-based materials (Lindberg et al., 2013): In addition the word 'natural' was added in order to see if the bio-based origin of the fibre-reinforced materials would affect the way the respondents perceive them. The final set of words included the following terms: natural, exclusive, eco-friendly, warm, soft, inexpensive, reliable, quality, pleasant, exciting and beautiful.

Material samples

Test specimens used in this study are shown in Figures 1-6. Twenty-one samples providing a wide range of different materials were used in the studies. The different material groups were: solid woods (oak and pine); metals (copper, brass, steel and stainless steel); wood fibre (oriented strand board (OSB), medium density fibreboard (MDF), cork); and fibre-reinforced composites including injection-moulded pulp and polylactide (PLA) or pulp and polypropylene, with different pulp content and colours (red, blue white and uncoloured). In addition, wood fibre-PLA (FIBROLON®), hot pressed pulp-PLA and a wood fibre-PP compound were included. Plastics tested were acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polypropylene (PP), and Makrolon. Most of the materials are for sale on the market but some of the fibre-reinforced composites are under development. The ones still under development have wood pulp as fibre reinforcement. The samples were cut into pieces 5 cm x 9 cm in size. The size allows an easy examination in the hands of the subject.

Figure 1. Fibre-reinforced composites, specifically pulp composites. From top left: Yellow hot pressed pulp-PLA, injection-moulded PLA with a sheet of yellow hot pressed pulp-PLA on top. The hot pressed production process gives the materials a surface where the pulp fibres can be felt when touching the surface, which makes the materials feel dry.

Figure 2. Fibre-reinforced composites, specifically injection-moulded wood/pulp composites. From top left: white injection-moulded pulp-PLA, uncoloured injection-moulded pulp-PLA, red injection-moulded pulp-PLA, blue injection-moulded pulp-PLA, white injection-moulded pulp-PP, Fibroton®, and wood fibre-PP. All samples were injection-moulded in the same tool, which gave them all a smooth untextured glossy surface and the fibres in the materials can't be felt when touching them.

Figure 3. Solid woods, from left: Oak and pine.

Figure 4. Wood fibre, from left: Cork, OSB, MDF.

Figure 5. Plastics, from left: Makrolon, ABS, PP.

Figure 6. Metals, from left: Steel, stainless steel, copper and brass.

Procedure

Data was collected in two rounds with two different groups of paid volunteers. Semantic assessments were gathered from a panel of respondents (n=30). A second data collection concerned sensorial assessments from a new panel of respondents (n=34). The reason for not consulting the same group for the semantic and sensory examination was to avoid carry-over and halo effects between experiments. The test persons in both groups were mostly students with varying backgrounds and the mean age for both groups was the same, 29 years.

Both experiments were conducted in laboratory setting with neutral surroundings. The participants were asked to wash his/her hands before starting in order to make sure no hand cream or finger grease would influence the tactile evaluation. The participants were seated at a table with the material samples placed in a pile in front of them. They were then instructed to evaluate the material samples one at a time and indicate their response on a score sheet, one sheet for each sample. They were free to touch and

Figure 7. Test setup. The respondents were instructed to evaluate one sample at a time. They took one sample from the pile to their left, evaluated it and then put it in a pile to their right.

look at the materials as they pleased, but were instructed to only evaluate the front surface of the material when it came to the visual and tactile properties. They were instructed to put the evaluated sample in a pile to their right and to continue with the next sample from the left in order to not compare the different samples to each other. The samples were cleaned and randomized between each respondent. See Figure 7 for test setup.

For the semantic study, 30 novice respondents, 18 women and 12 men, between the ages of 25 and 39 (mean age = 29) were recruited from a population of students or newly graduated academics in Stockholm. The samples were presented in random order, one at a time. The respondents were allowed to freely touch the sample. The words were presented on a written score sheet, one sheet for each sample. A 7-point Likert scale was used. The respondent selected an integer between 1 and 7, where 7 meant that the word was strongly

associated with the sample and 1 that the word was not associated with the sample. See Table 1 for details.

The sensory study was performed according to a similar protocol. The panel consisted of 34 respondents, 27 female and 7 male, between the ages of 20 and 51 (mean age = 29). A bipolar adjective scale ranging from -4 to plus 4 was used (Table 1). The respondents were students at university level or university staff of the University of Gävle.

Results

Average (arithmetic means) and the correlation (Pearson's) between the respondents were calculated. In order to estimate the degree of agreement between the respondents in each study.

Semantic evaluation: The overall inter-individual correlation ($n=30$) across all semantic ratings and samples was rather low ($r=0.35$; $p<.05$). The average inter-individual correlation coefficients for separate scales are shown in Table 1. Only two correlations are significantly above zero: *Natural* and *Eco-friendly*, indicating that the respondents were fairly consistent with each other in rating these attributes. However, the remaining semantic attributes received rather little consensus, indicating that these attributes were interpreted differently by the respondents or had a high level of subjectivity attached to them. For example, the attribute *Pleasant* had a close to zero correlation, indicating that this is a highly subjective attribute. An analysis of variance was performed on the data separated for gender (12 men and 18 women). Results indicate some differences in scaling behaviour. This difference is mainly a difference in level, i.e. men having higher average scale values on *Beautiful*, *Soft*, *Quality* and *Pleasant* scales. Men rated Makrolon and PP to be significantly more Beautiful and Exclusive than the female group ($p>0.5$). However, the correlations between the scales obtained from the two

Table 1. Descriptors used for the semantic and sensorial studies. Data were collected from test panels in both studies. In the semantic study the test panel consisted of 30 respondents and in the sensorial study the number of respondents was 34.

Semantic descriptors	Consistency across respondents (r)		Sensorial descriptors	Consistency across respondents (r)
Natural	0.68*	Tactile properties	Hard-Soft	0.58*
Exclusive	0.32		Smooth-Rough	0.76*
Warm	0.45		Low friction-High friction	0.16
Eco-friendly	0.57*		Dry-Fat	0.2
Inexpensive	0.21		Cold-Warm	0.63*
Beautiful	0.27		Rigid-Elastic	0.4
Soft	0.45		Brittle-Ductile	0.29
Quality	0.44		Strong-Weak	0.46
Exciting	0.21		Light-Heavy	0.65*
Pleasant	0.16	Visual properties	Matte-Glossy	0.75*
			Non-reflective-Reflective	0.78*
			Opaque-Transparent	0.91*
			No pattern-Much pattern	0.78*

*Marked correlations are significant at $p<.05$

Figure 8. Mean semantic attribute scores for each material group. Error bars represent 95% confidence interval around the mean.

groups are high, ($r=0.73-0.96$) indicating similar ratings of the different samples.

Sensorial evaluation: For the sensorial evaluation ($n=34$), the overall inter-individual correlation ($n=34$) for all scales was moderate ($r=0.56$; $p<.05$). The inter-individual correlation coefficients for separate scales were significantly above zero for eight of the rated sensorial properties, indicating a higher degree of agreement for these attributes. Some of the sensorial attributes received low correlation coefficients, e.g. *Brittle-Ductile* ($r=0.29$) and *Low friction-High friction* ($r=0.16$). These attributes may have been less well understood, e.g. Friction, or have shown small amount of variation in the sample set. A similar difference in scaling behaviour between genders as in the semantic case was noted, i.e. men using higher numbers. However, the ratings of the men followed the same pattern as the ratings of the women.

In this group only seven out of 34 participants were men and thus we cannot state if the differences observed are due to gender differences or individual differences.

Semantic and sensorial evaluation for each material group

Figure 8 shows the mean ratings and confidence intervals of each semantic attribute for each material group. The different groups of materials tend to have different profiles. Solid wood and Wood fibre groups are characterised by Natural and Eco-friendly whereas the metals are signified by Quality, Exclusive and Beauty. The Wood/pulp composite group shows little variation among semantic attributes. Pleasant and Inexpensive, however, received highest ratings among the attributes, although levels are generally low. The composite group exhibits a profile quite similar to that of the pure plastic group

Figure 9. Mean sensorial attribute scores for each material group. The sensory scales were bi-polar, the antonym of the descriptor in the legend is located at scale value one. Consult Table 1 for antonyms. Error bars represent 95% confidence interval around the mean.

Figure 9 shows the mean ratings and confidence intervals of each sensorial attribute for each material group. The different groups of materials have distinct profiles across the sensorial attributes. Metals, for example, are very much characterised by the optical scattering capabilities of these materials (perceived Gloss and Reflectance) and their perceived weight (Heavy). Again the wood/pulp composites have a similar profile to plastics but with two exceptions. The composites are perceived to be patterned to a larger extent and less glossy and reflective than plastic.

Factor analysis

Factor analysis, extraction method principal components, was performed in order to identify and compute underlying dimensions of the associated semantic descriptors. Two factors were extracted in accordance with the Kaiser criterion that eigenvalues

should exceed 1. The eigenvalues showed that the first factor explained 56% of the variance and the second factor 29% of the variance, for a combined 85%. A varimax rotation provided the best defined factor structure. The factor names were interpreted by analysing the factor loadings in Table 2. Factor 1 is identified by Exclusive, Quality and Beautiful which all have high positive loadings on the first factor and we named this factor 'Quality'. The second factor is identified by the words Natural, Eco-friendly and Warm and we named this factor 'Naturalness'.

The factor scores are composite variables, which provide information about a material sample's placement on the factors, as shown in Table 3. In particular the metals have high scores on Factor 1 (Quality). Oak scores high on Factor 1 but also on Factor 2 indicating that oak is associated with both

Quality and Naturalness. Among the composites, only the blue pulp-PLA composite has moderately high positive scores on the Quality factor, while the remaining composite and plastic materials score low or negative on both Quality and Naturalness factors. The materials defining the Naturalness factor with high positive factor scores are cork, pine, OSB, oak and MDF board.

A correlation analysis was performed in order to relate the sensorial evaluation of the samples to the Quality and Naturalness factors derived from the evaluation

Table 2. Factor Loadings (varimax raw) for variables. Extraction: Principal components.

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Commonality
	Quality	Naturalness	
Natural	0.1312	0.9244	0.8717
Exclusive	0.9695	-0.1696	0.9687
Warm	-0.1742	0.8748	0.7956
Eco-friendly	-0.0684	0.9543	0.9155
Inexpensive	-0.9114	-0.3486	0.9523
Beautiful	0.9480	0.1844	0.9327
Soft	-0.5871	0.6592	0.7793
Quality	0.9567	-0.1042	0.9261
Exciting	0.9217	0.0564	0.8528
Pleasant	0.7481	-0.0825	0.5665
Eigenvalue	5.7	2.9	
Percent explained	57.1	28.5	

Table 3. Factor scores for material samples.

Sample	Factor 1	Factor 2
	Quality	Naturalness
OSB	0.11236	1.61808
Pulp-PLA (hot pressed top, yellow)	-1.40189	-0.31028
Oak	0.91192	1.56584
Pulp-PLA (blue)	0.75796	-0.26090
Wood fibre (wood fibre- PP)	-0.48089	-0.28924
Makrolon	0.14428	-0.73985
Pine	0.43162	1.77402
Stainless	1.42413	-1.14042
PP	-1.41275	-0.97952
Pulp-PLA (uncoloured)	-1.03846	-0.50581
ABS	-0.66315	-0.85679
Pulp-PP (white)	-0.71140	-0.25470
Steel	0.81916	-1.21997
Pulp-PLA (white)	-0.64588	-0.53905
Cork	-0.36073	2.09547
Pulp-PLA (red)	0.12262	-0.39452
MDF	-0.94763	1.01201
Brass	2.09159	-0.38159
Pulp-PLA (hot pressed, yellow)	-0.05813	0.24659
Copper	1.71954	-0.31975
Fibrolon (wood fibre-PLA)	-0.81425	-0.11962

of materials using the semantic scales. The factor scores (Table 4) were correlated against the arithmetic means of the sensorial ratings. Sensory attributes Heavy, Glossy and Reflective show high correlation with the Quality factor. The negative sign indicates that the negative pole of e.g. Soft (Hard) and Warm (Cold) has correlation to this factor. The Naturalness factor is related to Rough, Friction, Warm and Pattern, as well as Dry, Matte and Non-reflective (the negative poles of Fat, Glossy and Reflective).

Discussion

Sensorial evaluations had more agreement between the subjects than the semantic dimensions. Sensorial properties are more directly connected to the material's technical properties and how the users perceive the material through his/her senses when interacting with it, and are therefore more constant. The affective meaning dimension is on the other hand influenced by factors other than the technical and sensorial properties of the material. Here the users' values, previous experience etc. come into play. So a larger variation between subjects was to be expected. Some differences in scaling behaviour between men and women were noted. Men generally attributed higher numbers in their scales thus generating overall higher average values. Although the ratings of men and women followed the same general pattern and were highly correlated, at some instances the ratings of the men were significantly higher than the ratings of the women, e.g. Makrolon and PP were judged higher in Quality and Beauty by men than by women. Gender differences in adult tactile perception need to be further investigated.

From the factor analysis, two factors were extracted: Quality and Naturalness with their respective associated descriptors, Exclusive, Quality and Beautiful for the Quality factor, and Natural, Eco-friendly, Warm and Soft for the Naturalness factor. The

Table 4. Correlation coefficients between the sensorial ratings and the sample factor scores on a 2D-solution.

(+ pole)	Factor 1	Factor 2
	Quality	Naturalness
Soft	-0.582*	0.416
Rough	0.333	0.778*
Friction	-0.209	0.717*
Fat	0.194	-0.606*
Warm	-0.578*	0.761*
Elastic	-0.611*	-0.009
Ductile	0.236	-0.592*
Weak	-0.696*	0.441*
Heavy	0.816*	-0.155
Glossy	0.603*	-0.672*
Reflective	0.621*	-0.656*
Transparent	-0.218	-0.337
Pattern	-0.053	0.819*
Weight	0.675*	0.254
Density	0.745*	-0.442*

*Marked correlations are significant at $p < .05$

Quality factor was defined by the metals and the Naturalness factor by the solid woods and wood fibre materials. Both metals, solid wood and wood fibre materials have strong material expressions that are rooted in what Hekkert & Karana (2014) call universal meanings. The result from the correlation analysis of sensorial evolutions to the two factors indicates which sensorial properties underlie the universal meanings of Quality and Naturalness. Quality is associated with Heavy, Shiny, Reflective and also Hard, Cold, Rigid and Strong. Metals have all these sensory properties. Naturalness is associated with Rough, Friction, Warm and Pattern, which all have high correlations with the factor and also Dry, Matte and Non-Reflective, which are sensory properties connected to both wood and wood fibre materials.

The results also present a challenge in that most materials in this study do not express both Natural and Quality at the same time. This is something that is consistent with previous studies by Karana (2012). Oak is the only material that is perceived as both natural and of high quality. We suggest that this can be due to the weight of the material, oak is heavy compared to many other woods and the results of the factor analysis show that weight correlates to the dimension Quality. But oak has also been used in exclusive interiors, parquet floors etc., which generated meanings such as exclusiveness and quality. These are learned meanings that have become very strongly connected to this material, so that even in a context-free setting these meanings are still dominant.

In both studies the materials were tested without a context, i.e., without a product and user setting. The results of the two studies indicate that these new fibre-reinforced composites do not stand out among other materials. Most of them are perceived as neither natural nor high in quality and are ranked close to many of the different plastic materials in the two studies. This supports Hekkert and Karana's idea that newer materials do not have universal meanings. The shy personality that Ashby and Johnson talk about is indeed reserved and it is up to the designer to get to know the material and make the shy personality become more expressive so that the material stands out from other materials.

The only one of the samples that stands out is the blue injection-moulded pulp-PLA sample that has moderately high scores in the dimension Quality. This suggests that colour influences this dimension.

The results show that these bio-based composites, whether reinforced by pulp or wood fibres (e.g. sawdust), at least in the shape of flat material samples, do not have a strong unique quality that the respondents could differentiate from plastics. This suggests that other factors such as colour, shape, surface structure, type of application (i.e., product), context of use and marketing will have a strong influence on how the material will be perceived. The different ways we will come to use these materials will influence the learned meanings we in time will connect with them. This makes it even more important to make further studies on how and where to use

them. The similarity to plastic can be a problem if these bio-based composites are to be understood by the users as eco-friendly, renewable materials. Plastics are fossil based and therefore not renewable and there are a number of reports on how plastics contribute to the pollution of our planet. Therefore there is a need to differentiate the fibre-reinforced composites that are bio-based and renewable from plastics. The only way to be certain that they will express the intended meanings is to understand and study the different factors that contribute to this expression.

The similarity to plastics can also help us understand more about how a material's expression, i.e., the different learned meanings, are formed. By looking at the history of plastics we can gain a lot of insight into how the way a material is marketed and used in different products influences the way we perceive it. Plastic materials started out being perceived as cheap and having low quality (Sparke, 1993). But their use in new revolutionary products, such as the practical hygienic food containers from Tupperware, that exploited the technical properties of the material, the meanings connected to plastic changed to be more positive and high in value (Cleminshaw, 1989).

Strategies for further studies

We suggest some strategies for further studies on how to get the wanted material expression of new pulp-fibre reinforced composites.

Technical properties

Use the material where the material's technical properties will be utilized the most. These properties are part of the shy personality that Ashby and Johnson talk about. For example, some of the fibre-reinforced materials will deteriorate over time and are even possible to compost. Instead of seeing this as a drawback, this can be an advantage in products with short 'in-use life', such as toothbrushes and packaging.

Fibres

The effect on the material expression connected to different amount of fibres in the composites was not studied in these tests. Karana and Nijkamp (2014) have shown that visible fibres play an important part in expressing naturalness in the material. But the fibres in the injection-moulded pulp-PLA materials are very fine in quality and not as visible as wood fibres and might not give the same results as in their study. This is something that has to be studied further.

Colour

The blue injection-moulded pulp-PLA composite had a moderately high score in the dimension Quality, but the white, uncoloured and red variations of the same type of material did not. This indicates that colours are important to express different meanings for these materials. Further studies on how colour affects the expression of these materials are needed. By comparing different pulp-fibre reinforced composites that have the same amount of fibre, all of which have the same surface and weight but differ in colour, we should be able to get a better understanding of how colour affect the meanings of these materials.

Surface structure

All the injection-moulded material samples had a smooth surface with no surface structure in these tests. This might contribute to them being perceived as plastic. Previous studies show that roughness plays a part in the meaning of naturalness. But it is not so straightforward that a rougher surface is perceived as more natural. It is an interaction between the surface structure, the fibres in the material and the shine of the material (Karana & Nijkamp, 2014). This means that there is a need for further studies on how different surfaces affect the expression of the injection-moulded pulp-PLA materials with fine quality fibres that are not that visible.

Associations from context of use

By using the materials in applications that in themselves have associations with eco-friendliness and renewability, there might be an effect of the associated meanings rubbing off on the materials, so that in time the materials themselves will be connected to these meanings. There is a need for further knowledge on how the interaction between product expression and material expression works.

Marketing

When a company release a new product on the market, it is marketed in different ways (for example commercials, social media, product placements etc.) to make the customers associate the product with meanings that make the product more attractive to them. Sustainability has become a marketing strategy for many companies because of growing environmental concern among consumers. As a consequence we see a lot of eco-labelling on consumer goods that has to do with the materials in the products, for example clothes made of eco-certified (GOTS, Ecolabel, OEKO-TEX Standard) cotton, packaging made of eco-certified paper (FSC) and furniture made from eco-certified (FSC) wood. These new pulp-fibre reinforced composites are made from renewable resources and it would seem obvious to market them as a sustainable choice and that a product made from this material would also utilize this as part of the marketing strategy for that product. Can marketing a new material as eco-friendly affect the way users perceive the material? Recent studies on taste of food show that the same banana tastes better when marked as eco-labelled instead of conventional (Sörqvist et al., 2015). Another study shows that the light from the same light source is perceived as more comfortable when presented as eco-friendly instead of as a conventional light source (Sörqvist et al., 2015). It needs to be studied if this eco-labelling effect occurs in the case of these new materials, so that the right marketing strategy for the material is used.

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